

Preparation and Characterisation of some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Titanium(III) and Chromium(III) with Phthalimide and Amino Acids

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Cyclic imides have wide applications in pharmacological¹ and industrial² fields. Amino acids are the building units of all proteins and enzymes and are intimately associated with metal ions in biological systems. Metal complexes of amino acids possess biological activities³. Mixed ligand metal complexes with cyclic imides and different amine bases have been prepared in our laboratory⁴⁻⁶. Recently, we have reported some mixed ligand complexes of iron(III) with succinimide and amino acids⁷. The present paper reports the preparation and characterisation of ten new mixed ligand complexes of titanium(III) and chromium(III) with phthalimide and amino acids (L-alanine, L-phenylalanine, L-leucine, L-tyrosine and L-proline).

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. All the complexes are insoluble in water and other common organic solvents but are soluble in DMF, DMSO and nitrobenzene. The molar conductance values in DMF ranging from 62 to 83 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicate that all the complexes are 1 : 1 electrolytes in nature⁸. From the analytical and physical data, the general formula of the complexes can be given as $\text{K}[\text{M}(\text{pim})_2(\text{aminoacid})_2]$.

An imide anion may be coordinated through its carbonyl oxygen or imido nitrogen (N). The negatively charged imido nitrogen is more likely to be coordinated to the metal ion and coordination through carbonyl oxygen is expected to be inhibited by steric hindrance⁹. The IR spectra of present complexes reveal $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ mode at $\sim 1700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ compared to $\sim 1735 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in free phthalimide⁵. This decrease in frequency may be due to the mass effect¹⁰. The observed $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{N}}$ mode of free phthalimide at 1310 cm^{-1} is shifted to $\sim 1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*/ (Colour)	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % :	
		Found/(Calcd.)	
		C	H
K[Ti(pim) ₂ (ala) ₂] (Lemon)	190	47.05 (47.57)	3.74 (3.62)
K[Ti(pim) ₂ (phe) ₂] (Buff)	215	57.29 (57.70)	4.06 (3.98)
K[Ti(pim) ₂ (leu) ₂] (Lemon)	175	52.85 (52.57)	5.20 (5.04)
K[Ti(pim) ₂ (tyr) ₂] (Cream)	220	54.77 (52.21)	3.64 (3.81)
K[Ti(pim) ₂ (pro) ₂] (Cream)	196	50.93 (51.40)	3.86 (3.98)
K[Cr(pim) ₂ (ala) ₂] (Green)	310	47.58 (47.22)	3.73 (3.60)
K[Cr(pim) ₂ (phe) ₂] (Blue)	284	57.49 (57.37)	4.10 (3.96)
K[Cr(pim) ₂ (leu) ₂] (Green)	318	51.66 (52.24)	4.82 (5.01)
K[Cr(pim) ₂ (tyr) ₂] (Green)	305	54.43 (54.90)	3.65 (3.79)
K[Cr(pim) ₂ (pro) ₂] (Green)	278	50.76 (51.05)	4.13 (3.95)

*pim = C₈H₄O₂N, ala = C₃H₆O₂N, phe = C₉H₁₀O₂N, leu = C₆H₁₂O₂N, tyr = C₉H₁₀O₃N, pro = C₅H₈O₂N

in the spectra of the complexes, suggesting thereby N formation and coordination^{5,11}. The complexes show strong bands at 3120–3280 (NH₂) and 1560–1590 cm^{-1} (C=O) indicating the coordination of amino acids through N and O donors¹². The complexes also show bands at ~ 1620 and $\sim 1390 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to δ_{NH_2} and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ modes. Further, the presence of M–N and M–O

bonds in the complexes are evident from the appearance of bands at 480–530 and 420–450 cm^{-1} respectively.

The observed values of effective magnetic moment of the titanium(III) complexes lie in the range 1.65–1.87 B.M. at room temperature which indicate their paramagnetic nature with one unpaired electron. The chromium(III) complexes have effective magnetic moments in the range 3.69–3.95 B.M. corresponding to three unpaired electrons, consistent with essentially octahedral stereochemistry.

The electronic spectra of the titanium(III) complexes in DMF gave one band at 19 500–20 920 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 18 519–19 000 cm^{-1} . The band is obviously derived from the transition ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ for an O_h symmetry. The electronic spectra of the chromium(III) complexes in DMF gave three bands at 17 360–18 000, 24 200–26 000 and 35 350–37 890 cm^{-1} corresponding to transitions ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and charge transfer respectively, which are typical for octahedral chromium(III) complexes⁶.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade (B.D.H.).

Aqueous solutions of metal(III) chloride and amino acid containing minimum amount of KOH to make soluble were mixed in a molar ratio of 1 : 2 and the mixture was stirred for 2 h. A solution of potassium phthalimide (2 mol) in water was then added to it dropwise with continuous stirring. The resulting clear mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 0.5 h and then left to cool. The crystalline product that deposited was washed with distilled water and finally with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Infrared spectra (film) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam Sp3-300 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a LKB Ultraspec K-4053 spectrophotom-

eter. Magnetic measurement was carried out on a Sherwood Scientific magnetic susceptibility balance. Conductivity was measured on a WPA CM35 conductivity meter having a dip-type cell with platinumised electrodes.

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